

AQ-WATCH

**METHODOLOGY TO ESTIMATE SURFACE AIR
POLLUTION FROM SATELLITE OBSERVATIONS**

Deliverable title:	Methodology to estimate surface air pollution from satellite observations
Deliverable number:	D2.3
Revision:	1
Status:	Final
Planned delivery date:	31/12/2021
Actual date of issue:	15/12/2021
Nature of deliverable:	Report
Lead partner:	BSC
Dissemination level:	PU(Public)

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 870301

About this document

Work package in charge: WP2: Exploitation and Visualization of Satellite and in situ Data

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Contents

1	Abstract /publishable summary	8
2	Conclusion & Results	8
3	Project objectives	8
4	Detailed report on the deliverable	10
4.1	Context and objectives	10
4.2	Data preparation	14
4.2.1	Surface in-situ NO ₂ observations	14
4.2.2	TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns	14
4.2.3	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) land cover data	15
4.2.4	ECMWF ERA5 meteorological data	16
4.2.5	Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) population data	16
4.2.6	CAMSRA global chemical reanalysis (EAC4)	16
4.3	Methodology	17
4.3.1	Workflow	17
4.3.2	Coding and computational aspects	17
4.3.3	Machine learning (ML) modeling	19
4.3.4	Estimation of the expected performance	20
4.3.5	Area of applicability	20
4.3.6	Comment on the quality of the TROPOMI NO ₂ data	22
4.4	Illustration of the results over Santiago de Chile region	23
4.4.1	Description of the target region	23
4.4.2	Relationships between NO ₂ surface concentrations and NO ₂ tropospheric columns	24
4.4.3	Evaluation of the ML-based predictions	25
4.4.4	Area of applicability	27
4.4.5	Prediction of surface NO ₂ concentrations	29
4.4.6	European Air Quality Index (eAQI)	32
4.5	Results over other regions	33
4.5.1	Denver and Front Range, Colorado	34
4.5.2	Po valley, Italy	38
4.5.3	Catalonia, Spain	43
4.5.4	Mexico City, Mexico	48
4.6	Discussion and conclusion	52
4.7	Release of the product prototype for future exploitation	54
5	References	55
6	Dissemination and uptake	57
6.1	Uptake by the targeted audience	57
6.2	This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience	57

7 Deliverable timeliness	57
8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	57
9 Sustainability	58
9.1 Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date	58
9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	58
10 Full track of dissemination activities	58
11 Full track of publications and IP	58
11.1 Peer reviewed articles	58
11.2 Publications in preparation or submitted	58
11.3 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable:	58

List of Figures

1	Atmospheric composition EO observation assimilated in CAMSRA chemical reanalysis (taken from Inness et al. (2018)).	17
2	Workflow of the methodology for estimating NO ₂ surface mixing ratios.	18
3	Illustration of the nested k-fold CV (here with k=3)	21
4	Annual average of most important input features. Cells containing surface NO ₂ monitoring stations are indicated with black borders.	24
5	Daily 1-hour maximum NO ₂ mixing ratios at the 19 monitoring stations of Central Chile (in grey) and corresponding average (in green).	25
6	TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO ₂ mixing ratios over Santiago de Chile region, at different time scales.	26
7	Correlations (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from linear regressions of TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO ₂ mixing ratios at daily scale, computed for each season and month, over the Santiago de Chile region.	27
8	Dissimilarity index (DI) over the Santiago de Chile region. The overall DI is shown (top left panel) together with the DI associated to most important features (other panels). Cells with surface stations are shown in black.	29
9	Seasonal average of ML-based daily 1-hour maximum surface NO ₂ mixing ratio over the Santiago de Chile region.	30
10	Monthly average of ML-based daily 1-hour maximum surface NO ₂ mixing ratio over the Santiago de Chile region.	31
11	Table to convert air pollutant concentrations into eAQI (source : https://www.euronews.com/weather/copernicus-air-quality-index).	32
12	Monthly average of ML-based NO ₂ eAQI over the Santiago de Chile region.	33
13	TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO ₂ mixing ratios, at different time scales, over Denver, Colorado region.	34
14	Correlations (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from the scatter plots of TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO ₂ mixing ratios at daily scale, computed for each season and month, over Denver, Colorado region.	35
15	Dissimilarity index (DI) over Denver, Colorado region, overall and for a subset of features.	36
16	Seasonal average of the ML-based surface NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Denver, Colorado region.	37
17	TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO ₂ mixing ratios, at different time scales, over the Po valley, Italy.	39
18	Correlations (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from the scatter plots of TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO ₂ mixing ratios at daily scale, computed for each season and month, over the Po valley, Italy.	40
19	Annual ML-based surface NO ₂ mixing ratio, DI, TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns and surface NO ₂ observations over the Po valley region.	40
20	Monthly average of ML-based surface NO ₂ mixing ratios over the Po valley region.	41
21	Monthly average of ML-based NO ₂ eAQI over the Po valley region.	42

22	TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO ₂ mixing ratios, at different time scales, over Catalonia, Spain.	44
23	Pearson Correlation Coefficients (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from the scatter plots of TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO ₂ mixing ratios, computed for each season and month, over Catalonia, Spain.	44
24	Dissimilarity index (DI) over Catalonia, Spain.	45
25	Annual average of the ML-based surface NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum (top left panel) and eAQI (top right panel), and TROPOMI tropospheric columns (bottom left panel) and surface NO ₂ observations (bottom right panel), over Catalonia, Spain.	45
26	Monthly average of the ML-based surface NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Catalonia, Spain.	46
27	Monthly average of the eAQI over Catalonia, Spain.	47
28	Annual average of ML-based surface NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum, TROPOMI NO ₂ tropospheric columns, surface in-situ NO ₂ concentrations and CAMSRA NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Mexico City.	49
29	Annual average of ML-based surface NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum when selecting dissimilarity index values below 1.5 (rather than 1.0).	50
30	Monthly average of the ML-based surface NO ₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Mexico City region.	50
31	Monthly average of the NO ₂ eAQI over Mexico City region.	51
32	Annual average of ML-based surface NO ₂ concentrations, without (left panel) and with (right panel) OpenStreetMap road density features, over the Santiago de Chile region.	53

List of Tables

1	Statistical results of the GBM model over Santiago de Chile region.	27
2	Statistical results of the GBM model over Catalonia.	43
3	Statistical results of the GBM model over Mexico City.	48

1 Abstract /publishable summary

Monitoring and mitigating air quality primarily requires quantifying the spatial and temporal variability of pollutant concentrations at the surface where adverse impacts on health and vegetation are of strongest interest. Given the persistent uncertainties of physics-based air quality models and the intrinsic limitations of observational dataset such as surface in-situ observations or space-based tropospheric column measurements, new innovative approaches are required to take benefit from these valuable information while at the same time overcome their respective limitations. In this work, we developed a machine-learning-based methodology to estimate surface nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) concentrations based on space-based TROPOMI observations and surface in-situ NO₂ observations, combined with a variety of ancillary global-scale dataset. In order to demonstrate its general applicability but also to highlight some of its limitations, we applied it to several case studies in different regions of the world (Chile, Colorado, Italy, Spain, Mexico). The corresponding Python software is entitled SAMARITAN (which stands for *Space-bAsed Monitoring of AiR qualITy using mAchine learniNg*) and will be made publicly available. Although still at the prototype level, it provides a valuable example of EO downstream application of potential interest in many regions where surface in-situ observations are too scarce and physics-based air quality modeling systems too uncertain.

2 Conclusion & Results

This deliverable provides (1) a contextualisation of the initial problem related to the persistent lack of reliable information regarding the spatio-temporal variability of pollutant concentrations at the surface, (2) a detailed description of the innovative methodology designed to address this issue based on a variety of high-quality EO and non-EO products, and (3) a set of several case studies in different regions of the world where this methodology has been deployed, generally with encouraging results despite some persistent limitations. The main tangible achievement of this work is the so-called SAMARITAN software (*Space-bAsed Monitoring of AiR qualITy using mAchine learniNg*) developed in the frame of the AQ-WATCH project and that will be publicly released in 2022. This deliverable is for the general public and endeavours to discuss transparently both the potentials and limitations of the methodology. Actors operating in the field of air quality and interested in developing and exploiting such innovative EO downstream applications will benefit from the large experience gained along this development phase.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
[1] To design and produce new global and regional air pollution atlases that include the climatological distribution of chemical pollutants complemented by quantities such as the diurnal and seasonal variations, air quality and related health indices, premature mortality exceedance frequency, long-term trends, etc.	Yes
[2] To develop software packages with the capability to provide more accurate daily forecasts of air quality at the regional scale including tailored high-resolution fire smoke and wind-blown dust forecasts; downscaling of air quality forecasts to 2 km resolution in urban areas.	No
[3] To develop a source apportionment service to mitigate air pollution and hence increase the life expectancy of the population in different regions of the world, with special focus on the role of agricultural sources of air pollution and the potentially important effects of fracking operations.	No
[4] To develop a new tool-box that will be user-friendly and accessible to decision-makers to evaluate the efficiency of proposed mitigation measures in different industrial sectors on the resulting level of air pollutants in three different regions of the world. This will establish the basis for their wider adoption and generalization.	No
[5] To co-design, co-produce and co-evaluate for the first time prototype products and services with prime users in three regions of the world chosen for their specific level of economic, social and environmental development.	No

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package.

Objectives of WP2	Relevance in this deliverable?
2.1 Preparation of an air-quality dataset using satellite data downloaded from the WEkEO DIAS (Copernicus Data and Information Access Services). WEkEO is still under development: before it is fully operational, the data will be accessed through the Copernicus Atmosphere Data Store (available in July 2019) and through the Sentinel Hub EO browser (sentinel-hub.com/explore.eobrowser). The Copernicus Atmosphere Service retrospective reanalysis will also be accessed through WEkEO. As soon as all the observations are available in WEkEO, all data used in the project will be accessed through this system, complemented by third-party data for parameters not covered by Copernicus.	No
2.2 Develop an atlas including visualization of satellite and in-situ data as well as air pollution maps to assist monitoring and analyses of air pollution.	No
2.3 Use of satellite, surface observations and the CAMS reanalysis to provide global and regional climatologies of air pollution including statistical information (means, diurnal and seasonal variability, long-term trends, exceedances)	No
2.4 Develop an innovative method to calculate health indices and mortality from outdoor pollution using satellite observations	Yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Context and objectives

Air pollution is currently one of the strongest environmental issues with well recognized adverse impacts on health, vegetation and climate. **Mitigating air pollution first requires a quantification of the surface pollutant concentrations to which people and ecosystems are exposed, which primarily relies on surface monitoring stations able to provide reference measurements of pollutant concentrations.** Due to their high cost and the strong technical skills they usually require for installation, operation and maintenance, these surface monitoring stations are typically deployed in a very limited number, and are still completely missing in some developing countries. To fill the data gaps, the scientific community has put strong efforts over the last decades to develop sophisticated chemistry-transport models (CTMs) able to estimate pollutant concentrations with full spatio-temporal coverage (at a given spatio-temporal resolution). Despite continuous improvements, these geophysical models remain affected by substantial uncertainties, coming from a variety of sources, including emissions, typically one of the strongest and most uncertain driver of the variability of pollutant concentrations, together with physical and chemical processes and meteorology. In particular, **stronger emission uncertainties are expected in many developing countries due to insufficient high-quality local activity and socio-economical data and still limited research effort for building more reliable emission inventories. This can lead to strongly uncertain air quality (AQ) predictions, even with state-of-the-art CTMs shown to perform relatively well in developed countries**

from where they originate (e.g. Europe, North America, parts of Asia). In addition, since building reliable emission inventories is a complex and fastidious task requiring the aggregation of multiple data, such inventories are usually not updated annually, which adds another layer of uncertainty, especially in countries where technology, social behaviours and/or regulation are changing rapidly.

In this context, **outstanding opportunities have been offered by Earth Observation (EO) polar-orbiting passive space sensors for overcoming this lack of surface monitoring stations, especially since the 2000s when a number of successful EO missions brought a major step forward in our understanding of the spatial variability of air pollution at global scale.** While most past sensors were limited by their relatively coarse spatial resolution, the last-generation TROPOMI sensor on-board Sentinel-5 Precursor (S-5P) launched in October 2017 is now providing AQ observations at an unprecedented spatial resolution of $5.5 \times 3.5 \text{ km}^2$ (since August 2019, $7 \times 3.5 \text{ km}^2$ before), which is a factor 15 higher than its OMI predecessor. Besides the uncertainties of current retrieval algorithms and the fact that polar-orbiting satellites only provide one measurement at a given (and fixed) time of the day and under cloud-free conditions, **one of the most critical limitation of such passive space sensors regarding AQ monitoring lies in the fact that they can only provide tropospheric column measurements, while AQ applications typically require information about surface pollutant concentrations.** Depending on the pollutant (and in particular its chemical lifetime and the spatial distribution of its sources), tropospheric columns can be strongly de-correlated from surface concentrations and thus provide a misleading view of the spatio-temporal variability of surface air pollution. For instance, due to its relatively long chemical lifetime, carbon monoxide (CO) have strong background concentrations in the free troposphere, which considerably limits the ability of tropospheric columns to provide information about the variability of surface CO concentrations. The limitation is even stronger for ozone (O_3) due to a typically low sensitivity of current sensors to surface O_3 and the strong O_3 reservoir existing in the free troposphere and stratosphere. For these pollutants, such satellite observations can still help better assessing the surface pollutant concentrations, but only through complex data assimilation systems (coupled to the CTMs) eventually able to transport part of the observational information from the tropospheric column toward the surface. **This data assimilation approach is a very active field of research since the last decades, but the underlying level of complexity remains a strong barrier for many public and private actors interested in AQ monitoring** and the need for reliable emission inventories persists (although some data assimilation and inverse modeling techniques can also be used to better constrained these emissions).

Due to its relatively short chemical lifetime, NO_2 typically remains close to its emission sources, within the planetary boundary layer (PBL). This explains why NO_2 tropospheric columns and surface concentrations are typically considered to be reasonably well correlated. Although a comprehensive analysis with sufficient spatio-temporal representativeness is still missing in the scientific literature, some first studies recently investigated the co-variability of TROPOMI NO_2 tropospheric columns and collocated surface NO_2 concentrations measured by AQ monitoring networks. For instance, on annual average (2019) over United-States, Goldberg et al. (2021) reported a spatial correlation R^2 of 0.66.

Several factors may de-correlate NO_2 tropospheric columns and surface concentrations, the most important ones being likely the intensity of the surface emissions and the impact of the meteorological conditions on its vertical mixing. The PBL height and the vertical mixing effi-

ciency can directly affect the relationship between both variables. The horizontal advection of NO₂-polluted air masses in altitude (within or above the PBL) is evidently another source of de-correlation, although this is partly limited by the short chemical lifetime of NO₂. Lightning are another well-known natural source of NO_x emissions in the free troposphere and can thus also play a role, but probably at a second order compared to surface anthropogenic sources, especially above urban areas.

In this context, the development of alternative data-driven approaches able to take benefit from these space-based columnar observations to extract observational information representative of the surface conditions is of strong interest, especially (but not exclusively) in regions with relatively scarce surface monitoring stations. The key objective of the present work is to explore the use of machine learning (ML) algorithms for learning the relationships between surface concentrations and tropospheric columns in order to estimate these surface pollutant concentrations in areas where no surface observations are available.

Even for pollutant like NO₂, these column-to-surface relationships are quite complex and the use of ML thus offers an interesting alternative approach for learning about these relationships based on the historical data available. Over the last decade, a growing attention has been put on these ML algorithms due to the good predictive skills they showed in a wide range of applications and fields. Capturing the complexity of the column-to-surface relationships with ML models requires taking into account a variety of ancillary data susceptible to explain at least part of these relationships. In this work, the ML-based methodology for estimating surface pollutant concentrations relies on a variety of heterogeneous input data (e.g. meteorology, chemistry, land use, population). Importantly, only global-scale, free and open-source dataset are considered in this work. This ensures the scalability of the methodology to different regions of the world, which is a fundamental aspect for commercialization as it extends the possible market for these AQ products. It is worth mentioning that scalability here needs to be understood from a technical point of view : we ultimately want the methodology to be used in any region of the world but the performance obtained in one region cannot be expected in another one, as it depends on the quality of the input data over the region, among other local factors. Although for a given variable, different dataset might be available from different institutions, we will here give priority to dataset provided by the Copernicus program. Besides giving credit to the strong effort and investments undertaken by the European Union over the last decades, this choice is more pragmatically motivated by the high-quality of the corresponding dataset, which are internationally recognized as the state-of-the-art, as well as the commitment of Copernicus to continue providing data through a full, free and open data policy, which is also a clear asset for a long-standing commercial exploitation.

Besides these global-scale dataset (used here as input features in the ML models), such a methodology requires local measurements of surface pollutant concentrations, typically obtained from AQ monitoring stations (although it could also involve dedicated measurement campaigns). Given the variety of chemical and physical conditions in the world, a ML model trained in a specific region will probably not be applicable to another region with very different characteristics. Even within a single domain, all predictions cannot be assumed to have the same reliability as some areas might be only poorly covered by training data. For instance, a ML model trained with NO₂ surface observations coming from urban and sub-urban monitoring stations is not expected to provide reliable predictions in areas such as mountains or oceans since the column-to-surface relationships there are expected to be different from the urban envi-

ronment. Therefore, the methodology proposed here should be understood as a way to extend, in a dedicated region, the limited spatial coverage offered by the typically sparse AQ monitoring network, rather than a way to estimate surface AQ in regions without any surface observations. It is worth mentioning that in cities and/or regions without prior knowledge on AQ, a first step would likely include the installation of a few surface monitoring stations, to get a first quantification of the prevailing pollutant concentrations in specific locations. The development of sophisticated physics-based modeling systems would likely occur much later, given the aforementioned complexity of such modeling systems and the need to first develop emission inventories of sufficient reliability (even in countries with long-lasting research on the topic, emissions usually remain one of the dominant source of error). In such a context, innovative data-driven approaches able to extend spatially the AQ information provided by these scarce surface stations can be of strong scientific and societal interest. **The work described in this deliverable should be seen as a first step toward the development of satellite-based capabilities for continuous monitoring of surface AQ.** Although it is built on the use of polar-orbiting space observation, it should be mentioned that the on-going first geostationary missions dedicated to AQ monitoring (e.g. Sentinel-4, TEMPO, GEMS) offer unprecedented opportunities to refine our knowledge and understanding of the evolution of pollutant concentrations at the Earth's surface, at least in the regions covered by these new observations (e.g. Europe, North America, Asia).

The present work mainly deals with the methodological aspects. As an application, we focus on NO₂ along the year 2019 as this short-lived pollutant with relative simple chemistry is expected to provide an upper range of the performance that could be expected. The methodology in itself can be easily translated to other pollutants like particulate matter (PM) but the performance for estimating surface concentrations would likely be deteriorated given the much larger complexity of aerosols (e.g. numerous emission sources and physical/chemical processes of secondary formation, longer lifetime allowing longer transport, deposition).

Surface NO₂ concentrations are estimated in a few regions of the world to discuss both the potential and limitations of the proposed methodology. We first focus on the Santiago de Chile (Chile) region for which a more detailed description of the approach is given. The methodology is then applied to a few other regions, including Denver-Front Range (Colorado, United States), Catalonia (Spain) and the Po valley (Italy). We were not able to get publicly available AQ data prior to late 2020 for Beijing so this region is not included in the study.

The different dataset used in this work are described in Sect. 4.2. The methodology is introduced in Sect. 4.3. The results obtained over the Santiago de Chile region are discussed in detail in Sect. 4.4.3 to illustrate properly the methodology. The results obtained in the other test regions are then given in Sect. 4.5. A general discussion and some conclusions are provided in Sect. 4.6.

The prototype product developed in this work consists in a Python software entitled SAMARITAN which stands for *Space-bAsed Monitoring of AiR quality using mAchine learniNg* that will be released in open-source in 2022. Useful information on these aspects are provided in Sect. 4.7.

4.2 Data preparation

Besides the surface hourly NO₂ in-situ observations from local AQ monitoring networks, the first step of this work consists in preparing the different input dataset that will feed the ML models, which includes :

- NO₂ tropospheric columns observed from the TROPOMI instrument
- CAMSRA global chemical reanalysis from Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service (CAMS)
- Land use data from Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS)
- Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) population density from the European Joint Research Center (JRC)
- ERA5 meteorological reanalysis from the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)

The basic set of input features used here is the following : NO₂ tropospheric column and surface elevation from TROPOMI, NO₂ daily 24-hour mean and daily 1-hour maximum concentrations from CAMSRA, surface temperature, surface wind speed, boundary layer height and surface pressure from ERA5, urban cover fraction from CLMS, population density from GHSL, day of the week and day of the year. In addition, we also included the urban cover fraction and population density averaged over the surrounding cells (average of 9 cells in total; to build so-called buffered variables).

4.2.1 Surface in-situ NO₂ observations

The measured surface NO₂ hourly concentrations come from the different regional AQ monitoring networks, namely the *Sistema de Información Nacional de Calidad del Aire* (SINCA; <https://sinca.mma.gob.cl/index.php/region/index/id/M>) in Chile, the Air Quality Service of the US Environmental Protection Agency (AQS US EPA; https://aqs.epa.gov/aqsweb/airdata/download_files.html) in Colorado, and the European Environmental Agency (EEA) AQ e-Reporting database in Europe (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/aqereporting-9>), the SEDEMA environmental agency for Mexico City (<http://www.aire.cdmx.gob.mx/>). Note that all these in-situ NO₂ observations are not always fully validated. Some very high values were for instance observed in Santiago de Chile dataset. Therefore, in this work, as a first simple precautionary measure, we removed the NO₂ concentrations exceeding 2 times the 95th percentile. When deploying this methodology in operational, a more careful quality assurance screening would obviously be required but is beyond the scope of our study.

4.2.2 TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns

The TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns observations are available at global scale every day at 13h30 local solar time, under cloud-free conditions. The spatial resolution of TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns was initially 7x3.5 km² at nadir, but was later (after August 2019) refined to 5.5x3.5 km². Currently, these data are only delivered as L2 products, i.e. along Sentinel-5

Precursor orbits. In order to be able to use these data, we developed a preprocessing tool for converting these products from L2 to L3 over any given curvilinear fixed grid, which requires several steps :

1. Data downloading : TROPOMI data were download automatically using the `dhusget.sh` script made freely available on the Copernicus Data hub (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/userguide/BatchScripting>). Only offline products (“OFFL”) were downloaded (not near-real time “NRTI” ones). Note that TROPOMI data can also be downloaded manually on the S-5P hub (<https://s5phub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home>).
2. Quality assurance screening : Only the TROPOMI data with quality flag (variable `qa_value` in TROPOMI files) above 0.75 were retained, following the recommendations provided in the TROPOMI NO₂ Product User Manual (<http://www.tropomi.eu/sites/default/files/files/publicSentinel-5P-Level-2-Product-User-Manual-Nitrogen-Dioxide.pdf>). This removes cloudy pixels (here defined as pixels with cloud radiance fraction above 0.5), part of the scenes covered by snow or ice, as well as pixels with errors and problematic retrievals.
3. Regridding : Each individual TROPOMI (orbit) file has been regridded on the target grid using the `xESMF` python package, using the conservative method (<https://xesmf.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>).
4. Merging the orbit files : There is a small overlap at the edge of neighbouring orbits, which requires a special treatment. At the corresponding grid cells, we computed the weighted average of the NO₂ tropospheric columns, with weights defined as the percentage of the cell covered each orbit (for instance, if a given cell of the target grid is fully covered by a TROPOMI pixel from one orbit and covered only at 50% by a TROPOMI pixel from the next orbit, the corresponding weights are 1/1.5 and 0.5/1.5).

We also extracted from the TROPOMI data the terrain elevation information (variable `surface_altitude` in the TROPOMI files). As it slightly varies from one orbit to another, we computed the average terrain elevation over all the TROPOMI files taken into account.

4.2.3 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS) land cover data

We downloaded the CLMS land cover data available at global scale at 100-m resolution (version 3.0; <https://land.copernicus.eu/global/products/lc>). This land cover data is currently obtained from the PROBA-V space sensor that should soon be replaced by data from the Sentinel-2 satellite. More information on this product can be found in the corresponding Product User Manual (https://land.copernicus.eu/global/sites/cgls.vito.be/files/products/CGLOPS1_PUM_LC100m-V3_I3.4.pdf). As these data are delivered by 20°x20° longitude-latitude tiles of 20160x20160 cells each (100-m resolution), the regridding phase using the `xESMF` python package is extremely time-consuming. To overcome this limitation, all tiles covering the domain of study were divided in 1°x1° longitude-latitude subtiles (1008x1008 cells), and the regridding phase was performed in parallel on each of these subtiles independently (each subtitle was regridded and projected on the target grid). All individual regridded tiles were then merged together.

From this dataset, we used only the urban cover fraction data (variable *urban-coverfraction-layer*), but more detailed information on the land cover is available (e.g. bare, crops, grass, moss, shrub, snow, tree, etc.).

4.2.4 ECMWF ERA5 meteorological data

The ERA5 meteorological reanalysis provided by ECMWF at the hourly scale was downloaded through the Climate Data Store (CDS) portal (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>). The ERA5 data is available at global scale at a spatial resolution of about 30 km (over 137 vertical levels, from the surface up to 80 km). It is obtained from sophisticated geophysical models and data assimilation systems ingesting a wide range of EO and non-EO observations. The ERA5 dataset currently covers the period going from 1979 to present time, most recent data being delivered with a typical delay of 3 months. More detailed information on this dataset can be found in the ERA5 documentation (<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/ERA5%3A+data+documentation>). In our work, we used a limited set of meteorological variables : surface temperature, surface wind speed, surface pressure and boundary layer height. Again, these data were regridded to the target grid.

4.2.5 Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) population data

Population is taken from the Joint Research Center's (JRC) Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) dataset, freely and publicly available at https://ghsl.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ghs_pop.php. This dataset provides population count (expressed in number of inhabitants per cell) at the global scale, at a spatial resolution of 1x1 km², (also available at 250x250 m²). We choose the most recent reference year, namely 2015. In terms of preprocessing, we reprojected these population data initially delivered on a World Mollweide (EPSG:54009) projection, on our target grid, in an exact way (i.e. taking into account the exact overlapping area between both grid cells).

4.2.6 CAMSRA global chemical reanalysis (EAC4)

The global CAMS chemical reanalysis is available at a 0.75°x0.75° longitude-latitude resolution and 3-hour temporal resolution. It covers a period starting in 2003. We downloaded the corresponding data and regridded it to our target grid. Additional information on this product can be found here : <https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-global-reanalysis-eac4?tab=overview>. This reanalysis ingests a variety of AQ-related EO observations (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Atmospheric composition EO observation assimilated in CAMSRA chemical reanalysis (taken from Inness et al. (2018)).

4.3 Methodology

4.3.1 Workflow

The general methodology is illustrated in Fig. 2. The workflow thus includes three main operations : (1) preprocessing all the data, (2) training and tuning the ML model, and (3) making predictions. The different dataset are preprocessed following the description given in Sect. 4.2. In our work, we consider only daily 1-hour maximum NO₂ concentrations (hereafter referred to as $d1max$ NO₂ concentrations) as the regulation on NO₂ is usually based on this time scale. Therefore, although TROPOMI observations are available at 13h30 LST, the ML models developed here are trained to predict the daily 1-hour maximum of NO₂ concentrations rather than the hourly NO₂ concentrations at this TROPOMI overpass time of the day. Also, since we are essentially interested in estimating air pollution over land where most important adverse impacts are expected (on health and vegetation), no predictions are performed over seas and oceans.

4.3.2 Coding and computational aspects

All the codes developed in this work are in Python 3.7, and include about 13,000 lines in total. Among the numerous Python libraries used, the most important ones are the following : *numpy* (Harris et al. 2020), *xarray* (Hoyer and Hamman 2017), *scikit-learn* (Pedregosa et al. 2011) and *xEMSF*.

Besides internal parallelizations within the Python routines (using the *multiprocessing* package), the preprocessing of the TROPOMI, ERA5 and CLMS input data (by far the longest step) is split into multiple small independent operations that can be executed in parallel over a large number

Figure 2: Workflow of the methodology for estimating NO₂ surface mixing ratios.

of nodes. This parallelization is managed using the *Autosubmit* open-source tool developed at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). *Autosubmit* allows to manage parallelization on supercomputers, satisfying several important requirements from the weather and climate community, including :

- **Automatisation:** Job submission to machines and dependencies between jobs are managed by *Autosubmit*. No user intervention is needed.
- **Data provenance:** *Autosubmit* assigns unique identifiers for each experiment and stores information about model version, experiment configuration and computing facilities used in the whole process.
- **Failure tolerance:** *Autosubmit* includes automatic retrials and ability to rerun chunks in case of corrupted or missing data.
- **Resource management:** *Autosubmit* manages supercomputer particularities, allowing users to run their experiments in the available machine without having to adapt the code. *Autosubmit* also allows to submit tasks from the same experiment to different platforms.

More detailed information can be found at <https://autosubmit.readthedocs.io/en/master/>.

All the developments discussed in the deliverable have been performed on the BSC's MareNostrum 4 (<https://www.bsc.es/marenostrum/marenostrum>) supercomputer. Through this development phase, it has not been possible to use the available Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) platforms (e.g. Wekeo, CREODIAS, Sobloo, Mundi web services) first because they were not fully operational at the beginning of the AQ-WATCH project, and more importantly because the development and use of the product prototype described here requires substantial storage and computational resources, which would have required a paying access that was not planned in AQ-WATCH. However, the code is entirely developed with open-source Python packages and tools, which should allow in principle its implementation on DIAS platforms where in addition, most of the largest input dataset used here (e.g. TROPOMI, CAMSRA) are already available. In order to allow a potential use and extended development in the near future, all the SAMARITAN code of this product prototype will be made freely available on Zenodo (see Sect. 4.7 for more details).

4.3.3 Machine learning (ML) modeling

A wide variety of ML models are available for supervised regression problems. In this work, we use the gradient-boosting machine regression (GBR) model, a popular ensemble method based on decision trees. A few other ML methods have been tested, including Lasso, Ridge and Elastic net models but GBR was found to give the best statistical results. A more exhaustive model inter-comparison study may eventually help improving further the performance. Although complex ML models typically have a low degree of interpretability, an interesting aspect of the GBR models is that they provide the so-called *features importance*, which is a quantitative measure of the importance of each input feature in the trained ML model. This features importance is expressed in percentage (the sum over all features is 100%). This will be of special interest when investigating the area of applicability, as discussed later in Sect. 4.4.4.

Machine learning models typically include two types of parameters, the model parameters and the hyper-parameters. Model parameters are internal parameters fitted from the training data (for instance, the coefficients in Lasso models or the weights in artificial neural networks). As GBR is a non-parametric method, the model parameters here correspond to the different decision trees created along the training of the GBR ensemble model. Hyper-parameters are higher-level adjustable parameters that are typically tuned following a given cross-validation (CV) strategy (for instance, the factor used in the regularization term in Lasso models, or the number of hidden layers, the activation function or the learning rate in artificial neural networks). The tuning of the ML models requires : (1) defining a set of possible values for the hyper-parameters of strongest interest; (2) specifying the CV strategy for training and validating the ML models; and (3) choosing a tuning procedure, either an exhaustive search in which all combinations of hyper-parameters combinations are tested (`GridSearchCV` function in *scikit-learn*; potentially very expensive computationally), or a sparser search in which only a given number of hyper-parameters combinations chosen randomly are tested (`RandomizedSearchCV` function in *scikit-learn*). Here, we retain the randomized search for tuning a limited set of GBR hyper-parameters (the maximum depth of the decision trees, the sub-sample, the number of estimators, the minimum number of samples allowed in a terminal node). These hyperparameters are searched through a 5-fold CV. Once the optimal tuning is found, a new and final GBR model is

re-trained over the entire dataset, in order to take full benefit from all the data available.

4.3.4 Estimation of the expected performance

Following the good practices in ML, the estimation of the expected performance is done using a so-called nested CV with two nested 5-fold CV, the first one (so-called the inner CV) for training and tuning the ML model, the second one (so-called the outer CV) for computing an unbiased estimate of the expected performance. This nested approach allows avoiding overly-optimistic estimates of the performance (for more details, see for instance the *scikit-learn* documentation : https://scikit-learn.org/stable/auto_examples/model_selection/plot_nested_cross_validation_iris.html). An illustration of the nested CV is given in Fig. 3, with the outer CV splitting the dataset into *training-validating* and *testing* sets, and the inner CV then splitting the *training-validating* set into *training* and *validating* sets.

It is important to understand that all these steps for estimating the expected performance are completely separated from the production of the final ML model that will be used to make our final predictions. Indeed, in a nested K-fold CV, a total of K final models are trained and tuned through an inner CV on their respective *training-validating* set (blue-purple in Fig. 3), and evaluated against their respective *testing* set (red in Fig. 3). Computing statistics on these K *testing* sets provides a more robust estimate of the performance that we could expect from our *ML methodology*, where *ML methodology* should be understood as the combination of the choice of ML model, the choice of hyperparameters to be tuned and the CV strategy for tuning them. In other words, this nested CV approach estimates the expected performance of our entire ML workflow, not the final production model to be used then. Note that a more simple approach would be to operate a fixed split on the dataset into a *training* set for training the model, a *validating* set for tuning its hyper-parameters and a *testing* set for estimating its proper performance. However, such an approach gives less representative results as it intrinsically depends on the arbitrary initial *training-validating-testing* split. Conversely, the nested CV approach allows to evaluate the results over all instances of the dataset.

4.3.5 Area of applicability

We previously detailed how the expected performance of our ML model can be estimated. However, it is essential to understand here that this performance does not correspond to the performance that we could expect from any ML prediction over our period and region of study. Rather, it gives the performance that could be expected under conditions close to those typically encountered in the *training-validating* dataset. As an example, a ML model trained and tuned only with urban coastal surface monitoring stations would likely not be able to make reliable predictions in remote mountain areas, simply because the relationships between the different input features and the surface NO₂ mixing ratios are likely very different. Similarly, a ML model trained and tuned only during the winter season would likely make poor predictions in summer. Once trained, the ML model can always make predictions at any location (it simply needs a value for each input feature), but the predictions should not be considered as reliable when it is used in a so-called “extrapolation-mode”, i.e. in a region of the *features space* not (or poorly) covered by the training instances.

Figure 3: Illustration of the nested k-fold CV (here with k=3)

This fundamental issue is unfortunately often ignored in many ML-based mapping applications. Although evaluating the performance through spatial CV provides some first insights, it cannot fully address this issue of the applicability of the ML model, simply because the data available for building the ML model are often covering a very limited area of the domain (the few cells where surface monitoring stations are available). Assessing the area of applicability of our ML model remains a tricky task due to the multi-dimensionality of the problem. To our knowledge, no standard and broadly accepted approach is currently available in the literature. In this work, we designed a relatively simple although intuitive approach for quantifying to which extent the input features at a given location are different from those used for the training phase (i.e. in cells where surface observations are available). The corresponding quantity is hereafter referred to as the dissimilarity index (DI) and is computed in three steps :

1. We first compute for each input feature the 3th, 50th and 97th percentiles (hereafter referred to as p_3 , p_{50} and p_{97} , respectively) of the values available in our training set (i.e. where surface observations are available)
2. Then, in each cell of the domain and for each input feature, if the mean feature value is X , we compute the distance D as $(X - p_{50}) / (p_{97} - p_{50})$ if X is above p_{50} and $(p_{50} - X) / (p_{50} - p_3)$ if X is below p_{50} . Such an asymmetric approach is chosen to take into account the non-Gaussian distributions of some features. Other definitions of D could be explored in the near future.
3. Finally, in each cell of the domain, we compute the sum of the distances D of all features, weighted by the respective importance of each of these features. The importance of each feature is one of the available output of the GBR model after the training phase (Sect.

4.3.3). Choosing another type of ML model would not give directly such an information on the importance of the different features, and would thus require the approach described here to be adapted.

This provides a static map of the DI that can then be used to discard some areas where the dissimilarity is considered too strong. Note that here, we are not considering the temporal dimension, although this could deserve some investigations in the future. Both choosing the 3th and 97th percentiles for the definition of the DI and selecting the DI threshold above which ML predictions should be ignored rely on arbitrary choices. Changing the extreme percentiles used to compute DI and/or the DI threshold will have a direct impact on the area where ML predictions are discarded. A low (i.e. strict) DI threshold would let large parts of the domain without predictions of surface NO₂ while a high (i.e. lax) DI threshold would increase the spatial coverage of ML predictions but at the cost of a deteriorated reliability. Here, we specify a DI threshold of 1.0. Since DI is computed based on the distance to the median from 3th and 97th percentiles, such a threshold ensures that areas where features are outside or at the extreme tails (below 3th or above 97th percentiles) of their distribution in the training dataset are discarded.

Such an approach for identifying areas of the domain where ML predictions are the most reliable offers a first response to the complex problem of applicability.

4.3.6 Comment on the quality of the TROPOMI NO₂ data

Since the launch of S-5P, a number of studies have evaluated the quality of the TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns against both ground-based and airborne NO₂ tropospheric columns measurements. Over the Canada Oil sands, Griffin et al. (2019) showed a good correlation between TROPOMI and ground-based NO₂ tropospheric columns ($r=0.70$) a 15-30% negative bias. Around New York City and Long Island Sound, TROPOMI were found to be better correlated with ground-based and airborne PANDORA NO₂ tropospheric columns measurements (r^2 of 0.84 and 0.92, respectively) (Judd et al. 2020). During the S-5P validation campaign over Belgium, based on coincident APEX NO₂ retrievals, Tack et al. (2021) also reported a good correlation of $r=0.92$ and a negative bias of -14%. A more extended assessment has been recently performed by Verhoelst et al. (2021), based on 19 Multi-Axis Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS), 26 Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change (NDACC) Zenith-Scattered-Light DOAS (ZSL-DOAS), and 25 Pandora instruments distributed globally. Regarding the NO₂ tropospheric columns, this study confirmed a negative bias, ranging from -23 to -37% in clean to slightly polluted areas, up to -51% in areas with strong NO₂ pollution. Most of these errors are random but the dispersion was found to exceed the mission requirements for the NO₂ tropospheric columns. Besides the persistent representativeness uncertainties of such comparisons, a substantial part of the TROPOMI errors is due to the coarse TM5 NO₂ a-priori profiles used for the S-5P retrieval, while a smaller part appears to be due to the treatment of cloud effects and aerosols.

Regarding the present study, the TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns is one among other input features used to predict surface NO₂ concentrations. The presence of any systematic generalized bias in all the TROPOMI dataset should not impact the predictive skills since GBM

models are insensitive to linear transformation of their input features. If some more complex partially systematic biases exist, such as the now well-established negative bias affecting TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns in areas with strong NO₂ levels, the impact on the performance of our ML predictive model is also expected to remain reasonable given that these ML models ingest other input features that can be used to at least partly take into account such intrinsic issues in the TORPOMI dataset. For instance, using the CLMS urban fraction in addition to the TROPOMI data, the GBM model may be able to learn different relationships between NO₂ tropospheric columns and surface NO₂ concentrations in urbanized and rural areas. Similarly, if TROPOMI errors are partly related to the meteorological conditions, the use of ERA5 data within the ML model can help overcoming potential meteorology-dependent uncertainties. This ability of ML models to at least partly handle systematic errors potentially affecting the input features appears as a very interesting property for the present work. However, it is worth noting that the presence of random errors within the input data is expected to deteriorate the performance of the ML predictive models.

4.4 Illustration of the results over Santiago de Chile region

This section gives a detailed analysis of the results obtained in the region of Santiago de Chile here chosen as an illustrative case study. Results obtained in several other regions are shown and discussed more briefly in Sect. 4.5.

4.4.1 Description of the target region

We consider a domain of 0.025°x0.025° longitude-latitude resolution (about 2.5 km) extending between 72°W and 69.5°W in longitude and from 34°S to -32.5°S in latitude, thus incorporating a large region around the Santiago de Chile metropolitan area (99x60 cells).

For information purpose, the annual average of several input features is shown in Fig. 4. The population and urban fraction maps highlight the extended Santiago de Chile metropolitan area, a second urban cluster around Viña del Mar/Valparaíso (300,000 inhabitants each) at north-west as well as several much smaller cities (e.g. San Antonio and Melipilla at west, San Felipe at north). This region is characterized by a strong and complex orography, with the Andes beginning very close to Santiago de Chile and extending over most of the eastern part of the domain, with altitudes exceeding 5 km. The ERA5 resolution is relatively coarse but allows to highlight some mesoscale meteorological patterns, including stronger temperatures over land at low altitudes, stronger winds over the ocean and the coast, and intermediate and low PBL heights over land and ocean, respectively. TROPOMI annual mean retrievals show very strong NO₂ tropospheric columns over and around Santiago de Chile (up to 20×10^{15} molec/cm² in the city center), and lower values (up to 5×10^{15} molec/cm²) at north-west in the Valparaiso province. The CAMSRA data show relatively higher NO₂ mixing ratios in the area of Santiago de Chile and lower ones above oceans (west) and mountains (east), but convey very little information due to their coarse spatial resolution (the distance between Santiago de Chile and the coast is about 100 km).

In total, 19 surface monitoring stations distributed in 18 cells of our target grid are available in 2019. Strongest d1max NO₂ mixing ratios are observed in and around Santiago de Chile, while

all coastal stations located in the Valparaíso province show much lower values. An overview of the d1max NO₂ time series at all stations is given in Fig. 5, highlighting a clear seasonal pattern with NO₂ peaking in austral winter.

Figure 4: Annual average of most important input features. Cells containing surface NO₂ monitoring stations are indicated with black borders.

4.4.2 Relationships between NO₂ surface concentrations and NO₂ tropospheric columns

In this section, we analyse the correlation between TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns and collocated surface NO₂ measurements. Results (Fig. 6) indicate that the correlation between both dataset is moderate at the daily scale, with a Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) of 0.64, but continuously increases when considering longer time scales, with PCC of 0.72, 0.76 and 0.96 at weekly, monthly and annual scale, respectively. Such a tendency is expected due to the progressive improvement of the signal-to-noise ratio. Note that the last panel at the annual scale corresponds to the spatial correlation of TROPOMI versus surface mixing ratios since each point of the scatter plot corresponds to one grid cell with at least one station (18 cells in total). At shorter time scales, although the correlations can be reasonably good, there is still an important scatter, in particular for surface NO₂ mixing ratios around 50 ppbv for which a wide range of tropospheric columns values are observed. Besides observation uncertainties, possible reasons for this scatter include varying NO₂ vertical distribution and differences of representativeness of the different surface monitoring stations.

We extend the analysis by computing the correlations, slopes and intercepts for all individual seasons and months (Fig. 7). The correlations remain relatively constant along the year (around

Figure 5: Daily 1-hour maximum NO₂ mixing ratios at the 19 monitoring stations of Central Chile (in grey) and corresponding average (in green).

0.6-0.7) while slopes and intercepts show some variability with low slope and intercept close to zero in winter and high slopes and negative intercepts in summer.

Therefore, despite the reasonably good correlation found between space-based NO₂ tropospheric columns and surface NO₂ concentrations, especially at longer time scales, a substantial scatter persists at shorter (daily, weekly or even monthly) scales. This demonstrates that column-to-surface relationships are too complex to be accurately represented by simple linear models, which justifies the need for a more complex model.

4.4.3 Evaluation of the ML-based predictions

Following the methodology described in Sect. 4.3, we built a ML-based model for estimating surface concentrations. In this section, we discuss the performance obtained over the Santiago de Chile region. As previously mentioned, the expected performance of our modeling strategy is estimated through a nested 5-fold CV. The outer CV is used to split the dataset into *training-validating* and *testing* dataset, while the inner CV is used to split the *training-validating* dataset into *training* and *validating* dataset. All successive *training*, *validating* and *testing* dataset are concatenated before being used for computing the overall statistics. As two CV loops are nested, each point of the dataset is used several times as *training* point and *validating* point. More specifically, it can be easily shown that with a k -fold CV strategy, each point of the dataset is used $2 * (k - 1)$ times for *training*, $(k - 1)$ times for *validating*, and 1 time for testing (see Fig. 3). In this frame, the statistics obtained over the concatenated *testing* dataset correspond to our best estimate of the expected performance of our ML modeling strategy. The statistics obtained over the concatenated *training* and *validating* sets are computed for information purpose, to check several aspects related to the following questions :

- Is the ML model able to accurately fit the *training* set? If the errors on the *training* set are very close to zero, it might be a sign of a potential overfitting. Conversely, strong training errors would highlight that our ML model is not adapted to the current problem,

Figure 6: TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO₂ mixing ratios over Santiago de Chile region, at different time scales.

which would mean that the input data used and/or the ML model chosen do not allow to accurately fit the target variable. In ML terms, we sometimes talk about a “bias problem”, and possible solutions to explore notably include testing more complex ML models.

- How much the performance is deteriorated from the *training* to the *validating* set? Although a deterioration is expected when going from the *training* to the *validating* set, a too strong deterioration might indicate that we face a so-called “variance problem”, meaning that our model is overfitting the *training* set and has thus limited generalization skills. Possible solutions to explore include getting more training data (when it is possible), adding some regularization to limit the overfitting, and/or testing other ML models.
- How much the performance is deteriorated from the *validating* to the *testing* set? Again, a deterioration is expected between the *validating* and *testing* sets, because the optimal tuning is chosen to optimize the performance on the *validating* set. However, a too strong deterioration would also suggest a model variance issue (overfitting of the *validating* set).

Results obtained over Chile are given in Table 1. They show relatively good skills on the *training* data with normalized root mean square error (nRMSE) and PCC of 25% and 0.95, respectively, without clear signs of overfitting. In comparison, the performance on the *validating* set is only slightly deteriorated, with nRMSE and PCC of 40% and 0.85, respectively, with similar results on the *testing* set. In their study over Germany (2018-2020), Chan et al. [2021](#) randomly splitted their dataset into 90% of the data for training and 10% for testing (no information is provided regarding the tuning) and reported a PCC of 0.80, which is consistent

Figure 7: Correlations (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from linear regressions of TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO₂ mixing ratios at daily scale, computed for each season and month, over the Santiago de Chile region.

Table 1: Statistical results of the GBM model over Santiago de Chile region.

	MB (ppbv)	nMB (%)	RMSE (ppbv)	nRMSE (%)	PCC	slope	inter (ppbv)	N
training	0.00	0.00	6.40	24.51	0.95	0.85	3.95	66512
validating	0.01	0.06	10.26	39.29	0.85	0.74	6.91	16628
testing	0.01	0.05	10.32	39.52	0.85	0.73	6.95	4157

with our results. Overall, predictions appear unbiased, but strongest surface NO₂ mixing ratios are underestimated, as shown by slopes around 0.7. Reproducing the high concentration episodes remains a challenging task for both physics-driven and data-driven models. In the case of the data-driven models, one important issue is the relatively small number of such high NO₂ concentrations available for training. All in all, this statistical performance is reasonable but cautious is required when interpreting these results, as will be discussed in the section.

4.4.4 Area of applicability

We saw in the previous section that the expected performance of our ML predictions of surface NO₂ is reasonably good. However, as explained in Sect. 4.3.5, such a performance cannot be expected in areas too different from the those where surface monitoring stations are available for training the model. In this specific case study, as surface NO₂ measurements are available in only 18 cells in the Santiago de Chile region (0.3% of the 60x90 = 5,940 cells of the domain),

the training and tuning of our ML model only relies on a very limited dataset.

The overall DI obtained over the Santiago de Chile region is given in Fig. 8, as well as the DIs associated to a selection of different features. The overall DI is the sum of all features' DIs. High DI values indicate areas where features take values far from those found in the training set and where ML predictions are thus likely less reliable. The DI reaches its highest values (around 2.5) in the eastern part of the domain, driven by the strong dissimilarity brought by the low pressures, cold temperatures and low NO₂ tropospheric columns prevailing over the Andes mountain region (see the mean distribution of these features in Fig. 4). This is mainly due to the fact that surface stations are only available at low to moderate elevations, where most Chilean people are living. Some dissimilarity is also found over the Pacific ocean due to the relatively strong winds compared to land. The urban fraction brings some dissimilarity due to the fact that most surface stations are located in cities, but the corresponding DI value remains moderate compared to the other features. Importantly, despite most stations are located in urban environments, the dissimilarity varies within the large urban area of Santiago de Chile, with more dissimilarity in the heart of the city compared to the rest of the agglomeration. This dissimilarity is mainly introduced by the population density feature and to a lesser extent the NO₂ tropospheric column: although there are several stations in the Santiago de Chile metropolitan area, it seems they are not located in the most densely urbanized part of the city where surface NO₂ may reach its maximum concentrations.

Figure 8: Dissimilarity index (DI) over the Santiago de Chile region. The overall DI is shown (top left panel) together with the DI associated to most important features (other panels). Cells with surface stations are shown in black.

4.4.5 Prediction of surface NO_2 concentrations

In this section, ML-based predictions are shown only over land areas with DI below 1.0 (oceans and seas are ignored whatever their DI value). Seasonal and monthly ML-based surface NO_2 concentrations obtained over the Santiago de Chile region are shown in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively. On annual average, d1max NO_2 mixing ratios range between about 10 ppbv in rural areas and more than 50 ppbv in the center of Santiago de Chile. A clear seasonal variability is highlighted with maximum values reached during austral winter (June-August). Although NO_2 estimates are discarded over a large part of the domain due to too high DIs, the spatial coverage is considerably extended compared to the initial 18 cells with surface observations. Importantly, we were able to obtain such a spatial coverage because surface NO_2 monitoring stations over this domain are distributed in relatively heterogeneous environments, from small urban areas to city center of large metropolitan area. This is a crucial aspect of our methodology to keep in mind since having too few stations or stations all located in a specific environment may strongly reduce the area over which predictions can be made with sufficient reliability, as will be shown in another region in Sect. 4.5.

Figure 9: Seasonal average of ML-based daily 1-hour maximum surface NO₂ mixing ratio over the Santiago de Chile region.

Figure 10: Monthly average of ML-based daily 1-hour maximum surface NO₂ mixing ratio over the Santiago de Chile region.

4.4.6 European Air Quality Index (eAQI)

To be more intelligible to the general public, air pollutant concentrations are often converted into Air Quality Indices. Although different definitions have been proposed by different institutions in the world, we will here use the European Air Quality Index (hereafter referred to as eAQI). These eAQI are used in Europe with both surface observations and CAMS operational AQ forecasts. They are computed for each individual pollutant following a given conversion table (Table 11), based on hourly concentrations for O₃, NO₂, SO₂ and 24-hour running means for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. The multi-pollutant eAQI then simply corresponds to the maximum (i.e. worst) eAQI among all pollutants considered. Also, these hourly eAQI are then eventually converted into daily eAQI by keeping the maximum (i.e. worse) hourly eAQI of the day.

POLLUTANT	INDEX LEVEL <i>(based on pollutant concentrations in µg/m³)</i>					
	1 Very good	2 Good	3 Medium	4 Poor	5 Very Poor	6 Extremely Poor
Ozone (O ₃)	0-50	50-100	100-130	130-240	240-380	380-800
Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	0-40	40-90	90-120	120-230	230-340	340-1000
Sulphur dioxide (SO ₂)	0-100	100-200	200-350	350-500	500-750	750-1250
Particules less than 10 µm (PM ₁₀)	0-20	20-40	40-50	50-100	100-150	150-1200
Particules less than 2.5 µm (PM _{2.5})	0-10	10-20	20-25	25-50	50-75	75-800

Figure 11: Table to convert air pollutant concentrations into eAQI (source : <https://www.euro-news.com/weather/copernicus-air-quality-index>).

Although this eAQI is designed to be used at the hourly or daily scale, we computed its monthly averages (Fig. 12). Therefore, cautious is required when interpreting these results as a region might have a good eAQI on a monthly average but with several days of poor eAQI. At the monthly time scale and considering only NO₂, a large part of the domain, along the coast, is found to be of good air quality all along the year. The Santiago de Chile city reaches an air quality considered as poor from April to August, the corresponding area being the most extended in July. Over that period, a large area around the city, from south to north, shows a medium air quality. During the austral summer, only the center of Santiago de Chile remains affected by such a medium air quality, while most of the domain has an air quality considered as good.

Figure 12: Monthly average of ML-based NO₂ eAQI over the Santiago de Chile region.

As a conclusion, we illustrated in this section the potential of our product prototype for delivering information about surface AQ, using satellite observations representative of the entire tropospheric column combined with a variety of ancillary variables freely available at the global scale. From a relatively limited number of surface monitoring stations, we have been able to estimate surface NO₂ over a much more extended area. In the next section, we apply this approach to a few other regions of the world, in order not only to further validate our methodology but also to illustrate some of its possible limitations that have not arisen with this Santiago de Chile case study.

4.5 Results over other regions

This section presents and discuss more briefly the results obtained in other regions.

4.5.1 Denver and Front Range, Colorado

We consider a domain of $0.025^\circ \times 0.025^\circ$ longitude-latitude resolution extending between 105.4°W and 104°W in longitude and from 38.4°N to 40.8°N in latitude, thus incorporating the Denver metropolitan area and its surrounding region (55x88 cells). Only 6 surface stations, distributed into 5 grid cells, are monitoring NO_2 in 2019. Analysing the scatter plots between TROPOMI tropospheric columns and surface mixing ratios shows consistent results with what has been observed in Central Chile, namely an increase of the PCC with the time scale, from 0.47 at daily scale to 0.57, 0.72 and 0.80 at weekly, monthly and annual scale (Figs. 13 and 14). The estimated performance of the ML model is found to be very good, with no bias and nRMSE/PCC/N of 6%/0.99/13456, 22%/0.83/3364 and 23%/0.82/841 for training, validating and testing sets, therefore even better than the performance previously obtained in Central Chile.

Figure 13: TROPOMI NO_2 tropospheric columns against surface NO_2 mixing ratios, at different time scales, over Denver, Colorado region.

However, the specificity of this case study lies in the fact that (1) only very few stations surface stations are measuring NO_2 in this domain, (2) all stations are urban/suburban background, and (3) all are located in Denver city, not so far from each other. This likely explains the very good performance obtained since the spatial auto-correlation between these different near-by locations is probably strong. However, this also has dramatic implications regarding the area of applicability. Very high DI values are indeed obtained outside the center of Denver (Fig 15), thus limiting the potential validity of our predictions to the center of Denver, as shown on the

Figure 14: Correlations (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from the scatter plots of TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO₂ mixing ratios at daily scale, computed for each season and month, over Denver, Colorado region.

prediction maps (Fig. 16).

Therefore, our data-driven approach thus appears as of limited usefulness in the Denver region. Its application to this specific region nicely illustrates an essential aspect of the methodology proposed here : it requires not only a sufficient amount of surface NO₂ observations, but overall some heterogeneity within this surface data. Relying on very few stations is a first important issue, but here the most crucial issue lies in the fact that the available stations are all providing information on the same and very specific (at the scale of the entire domain) environment. As previously mentioned, our methodology allows to extend the spatial distribution of the surface AQ information provided by a limited set of monitoring stations, but the level to which this spatial distribution can be extended depends on the data available on surface.

Figure 15: Dissimilarity index (DI) over Denver, Colorado region, overall and for a subset of features.

Figure 16: Seasonal average of the ML-based surface NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Denver, Colorado region.

4.5.2 Po valley, Italy

We applied our methodology to the Po valley, in northern Italy, one of the most polluted area in Europe. We considered a grid of $0.025^\circ \times 0.025^\circ$ longitude-latitude resolution, and extending between 7°E and 14°E in longitude and between 43.9°N and 46.4°N in latitude (279×100 grid cells). Over the domain, 179 stations distributed into 172 grid cells are monitoring NO_2 .

TROPOMI NO_2 tropospheric columns are plotted against surface NO_2 observations in Fig. 17, and results from the linear regressions at monthly and seasonal scales are shown in Fig. 18. The correlation between both variables is 0.58 at the daily scale, and increases to 0.66 and 0.72 at weekly and monthly scales, respectively. Surprisingly, contrary to Chile and Colorado, the correlation at the annual scale is reduced to 0.64, thus even lower than at weekly and monthly scales. It is difficult to understand exactly such result but this might be at least partly due to specific cells on which surface monitoring stations and TROPOMI observations strongly differ in their representativeness. A still strong scatter is indeed observed at the annual scale, with for instance two cells showing similar surface annual NO_2 concentrations - 36 ppbv - but very different NO_2 tropospheric columns, namely 3 and 9×10^{15} molec/cm². It appears that the first cell is centered over the industrial harbour of Trieste and the second one in the suburbs of Milan. Therefore, in this specific example, the low NO_2 tropospheric column in Trieste harbour is likely explained by the fact that TROPOMI pixels cover here a substantial area of sea. At the hour of the TROPOMI overpasses (13h30), strong sea breezes are expected, which brings relatively clean marine air to the coast and might thus explain the low pollution observed by TROPOMI, while the surface monitoring stations could be impacted by a very local NO_2 pollution related to the harbour activity.

TROPOMI NO_2 tropospheric columns, surface observed NO_2 mixing ratios, DI and ML-based surface NO_2 mixing ratios are given in Fig. 19. TROPOMI data show a strong hot spot over Milan (with a maximum NO_2 tropospheric column of 11×10^{15} molec/cm²) that extends eastward along the Po river up to Verone, as well as a secondary hotspot on Turin. Low NO_2 tropospheric columns are measured over the Alps and the Apennines (the mountains of intermediate elevation on the western coast of Italy). The ML-based surface NO_2 mixing ratios highlight the most important urban areas of the domain. Interestingly the area with strong NO_2 tropospheric columns at the east Milan does not show very strong surface NO_2 mixing ratios (as observed at the surface monitoring stations). Given the large number of surface stations available over this domain, the spatial coverage of these ML-based estimates is large, with information missing mainly over the Alps mountains in north/north-west.

Monthly surface NO_2 mixing ratios are shown in Fig. 20, together with the monthly eAQI in Fig. 21.

Figure 17: TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO₂ mixing ratios, at different time scales, over the Po valley, Italy.

Figure 18: Correlations (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from the scatter plots of TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO₂ mixing ratios at daily scale, computed for each season and month, over the Po valley, Italy.

Figure 19: Annual ML-based surface NO₂ mixing ratio, DI, TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns and surface NO₂ observations over the Po valley region.

Figure 20: Monthly average of ML-based surface NO₂ mixing ratios over the Po valley region.

Figure 21: Monthly average of ML-based NO₂ eAQI over the Po valley region.

4.5.3 Catalonia, Spain

As a final case study, we applied our methodology to the Catalonia region in Spain, over a domain of $0.025^\circ \times 0.025^\circ$ longitude-latitude resolution, and extending between 1°W and 4°E in longitude and between 40.3°N and 43°N in latitude (200x108 grid cells). A reasonably dense NO_2 monitoring network is available, both in Barcelona city and entire Catalonia region, with 47 stations of different typology, distributed into 46 grid cells. Correlations between TROPOMI tropospheric columns and surface NO_2 observations are consistent with the results obtained over Chile and Colorado (Figs. 22 and 23). PCC reaches 0.59, 0.70, 0.76 and 0.82 at daily, weekly, monthly and annual scale. Over the different seasons and months, the PCC remains around 0.60. Slopes and intercepts follow seasonal variations close to those observed in Chile, with highest slopes and lowest intercepts during the cold season.

The ML model shows good prediction skills with nRMSE and PCC of 36% and 0.88 on the testing set (Table 2), thus quite consistent with the performance obtained in Chile. However, highest NO_2 values remain underestimated, with slopes around 0.80.

Generally, the DI takes relatively low values, with some exception over the Pyrenees mountainous chain along the French border, in the south-western corner of the domain as well as above the Mediterranean sea (Fig. 24). Over land, only the Pyrenees have DI values exceeding 1. The estimated surface NO_2 concentrations are shown at the annual scale in Fig. 25, together with the mean TROPOMI NO_2 tropospheric columns, surface observations and CAMSRA NO_2 field. As expected, Barcelona appears as the main NO_2 pollution hotspot in Catalonia, with annual NO_2 tropospheric columns up to 7×10^{15} molec/cm² in the city center, thus substantially lower than in Santiago de Chile (17×10^{15} molec/cm²) or Milan (11×10^{15} molec/cm²). This gives at the surface NO_2 concentrations up to 40 ppbv. In addition, results highlight multiple secondary hotspots in smaller cities (e.g. Zarragoza, Lleida, Sabadell in Spain, Andorra la Vella in Andorra, or Perpignan in France).

Monthly variations of ML-based surface NO_2 concentrations and eAQI are shown Figs. 26 and 27, respectively. The seasonal variability of NO_2 over Catalonia is relatively low, with NO_2 concentrations only slightly higher during late winter. On a monthly average, the worst eAQI are medium, mainly over the Barcelona metropolitan area, along the urbanized coast north of the city and in several intermediate cities.

Table 2: Statistical results of the GBM model over Catalonia.

	MB (ppbv)	nMB (%)	RMSE (ppbv)	nRMSE (%)	PCC	slope	inter (ppbv)	N
training	0.00	0.00	5.18	25.82	0.94	0.84	3.13	177872
validating	0.00	0.02	7.13	35.55	0.88	0.78	4.51	44468
testing	0.01	0.07	7.17	35.74	0.88	0.78	4.50	11117

Figure 22: TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns against surface NO₂ mixing ratios, at different time scales, over Catalonia, Spain.

Figure 23: Pearson Correlation Coefficients (PCC), slopes and intercepts obtained from the scatter plots of TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric column versus surface NO₂ mixing ratios, computed for each season and month, over Catalonia, Spain.

Figure 24: Dissimilarity index (DI) over Catalonia, Spain.

Figure 25: Annual average of the ML-based surface NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum (top left panel) and eAQI (top right panel), and TROPOMI tropospheric columns (bottom left panel) and surface NO₂ observations (bottom right panel), over Catalonia, Spain.

Figure 26: Monthly average of the ML-based surface NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Catalonia, Spain.

Figure 27: Monthly average of the eAQI over Catalonia, Spain.

4.5.4 Mexico City, Mexico

As a final test, we applied our approach to Mexico City, considering a domain extending from 100°W to 98°W in longitude and from 18.5°N to 20°N in latitude, with a longitude-latitude resolution of 0.025°x0.025° (79x60 cells). A total of 31 stations distributed in 31 grid cells are available, mostly located within the (very extended) Mexico City metropolitan area. Over that domain, on annual average, the maximum NO₂ tropospheric column reaches 18×10^{15} molec/cm² in the center of Mexico City, thus slightly higher than the maximum values found in Santiago de Chile.

The scatter plots between space-based NO₂ tropospheric columns and surface NO₂ concentrations show PCC of 0.51, 0.59, 0.71 and 0.76 at daily, weekly, monthly and annual scales, thus relatively consistent with those obtained in the other regions, although in the lower range. The expected performance estimated in Mexico City (Table 3) is also quite in line with the performance in the other regions, with nRMSE/PCC of 23%/0.79. However, the slope remains quite strongly underestimated (0.64), which again highlights the complexity of reproducing the strongest NO₂ surface concentrations.

Annual averages of ML-based estimates of surface NO₂ are shown in Fig. 28. The area of applicability is relatively limited, but still includes all the Mexico City metropolitan area. The main limitation in terms of applicability is related to the fact that all stations included here are located in Mexico City, which itself is located relatively high in altitude, above 2 km. Besides some mountainous/volcanoes of higher altitude (up to more than 4km), all the southern part of the domain has a lower elevation (below 2 km) and thus quite different meteorological conditions, as well as much lower NO₂ tropospheric columns. All these elements strongly limit the applicability of the built ML model. For information purpose, the more extended area of applicability obtained with a criteria of DI below 1.5 (rather than 1.0) is shown in Fig. 29 and highlights the Toluca and Puebla secondary cities. However, despite relatively strong NO₂ tropospheric columns observed north of Mexico City, at the border of our domain, ML-based surface NO₂ concentrations remain relatively low. These strong NO₂ tropospheric columns observed from space are located on the well-known Tula industrial complex (Rivera et al. 2009). This industrial area is characterized by low urban fractions in the CLMS data, contrary to the heavily urbanized Mexico City agglomeration where most of surface AQ monitoring stations are all located. This probably explains (at least partly) why our ML model does not predict strong surface NO₂ concentrations. This example again highlights the potential limitations of our approach and their requirements in terms of heterogeneity of surface in-situ observations.

Table 3: Statistical results of the GBM model over Mexico City.

	MB (ppbv)	nMB (%)	RMSE (ppbv)	nRMSE (%)	PCC	slope	inter (ppbv)	N
training	0.00	0.00	5.48	12.58	0.95	0.82	7.89	67456
validating	0.04	0.08	10.00	22.93	0.80	0.64	15.52	16864
testing	0.06	0.13	10.13	23.22	0.79	0.64	15.78	4216

Figure 28: Annual average of ML-based surface NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum, TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns, surface in-situ NO₂ concentrations and CAMSRA NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Mexico City.

In the absence of such observations in this specific industrial areas, it remains challenging to assess more precisely to which extent our predictions are from the actual levels of surface NO₂ pollution given that, in addition, most of the NO_x emissions in this areas are likely occurring in altitude, through the chimneys of the industrial facilities, which at least limits the levels of pollution at the surface compared to the tropospheric columns observed from space. In any case, this area of doubtful results is discarded by the DI threshold of 1.0, which illustrates how important it is to assess properly assess the area of applicability of our ML predictions.

The monthly average of surface NO₂ concentrations and eAQI are given in Figs. 30 and 31. A clear seasonal variability can be seen in Mexico City, with worst air quality labelled as poor during wintertime when monthly mean NO₂ mixing ratios greatly exceed 50 ppbv.

Figure 29: Annual average of ML-based surface NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum when selecting dissimilarity index values below 1.5 (rather than 1.0).

Figure 30: Monthly average of the ML-based surface NO₂ daily 1-hour maximum over Mexico City region.

Figure 31: Monthly average of the NO₂ eAQI over Mexico City region.

4.6 Discussion and conclusion

Over the last decade, the Copernicus program made freely available a variety of high-quality dataset related to air quality. However, each of these dataset alone suffer from specific limitations that prevent their direct use in applications where a detailed information on AQ at the surface is required (e.g. studies of the adverse impacts on health and vegetation). Passive sensors on-board polar-orbiting satellites like TROPOMI/S-5P indeed provide AQ observations at relatively high spatial resolution and with global coverage, but restricted to integrated tropospheric columns, and affected by several uncertainty sources. Conversely, CAMSRA provides a global-scale reanalysis taking benefit from both the physics and chemistry implemented in a state-of-the-art model and the assimilation of a variety of satellite observations, but at a spatial resolution far too coarse to be used for air quality studies at local scale, and also with substantial uncertainties.

In this work, we developed an innovative fully data-driven methodology for estimating surface NO₂ concentrations based on a synergistic use of in-situ observations from third-parties, EO dataset from Copernicus (e.g. TROPOMI tropospheric columns and CLMS land cover data), chemical and meteorological reanalysis (CAMSRA and ERA5, both ingesting already a variety of additional EO dataset) and GHSL demographic data. The corresponding product prototype overcomes the intrinsic limitations of each of these dataset to deliver AQ information at the surface at a relatively high spatial resolution.

After collocating in time and space TROPOMI NO₂ tropospheric columns with surface NO₂ measurements, we first showed that, as expected, TROPOMI observations already capture a substantial part of the spatio-temporal variability of surface NO₂ mixing ratios, especially when considering longer time scales (e.g. seasonal and annual). However, using these TROPOMI NO₂ observations alone as a proxy of surface NO₂ conditions comes with potentially strong uncertainties, depending on the importance of other factors such as the meteorology in the column-to-surface relationships. This motivated the development of more complex machine learning (ML) models able to represent more accurately these relationships taking benefit of (1) a variety of additional information coming from other dataset, as well as (2) the ability of such sophisticated ML models to fit complex multivariate non-linear relationships when trained appropriately and with a sufficient amount of data.

Using a nested cross-validation strategy, we estimated the expected performance of our ML models. Results were found to be usually reasonable with RMSE around 25-40% and PCC typically around 0.75-0.85 on testing dataset. We also discussed the limitations of these cross-validation statistics for assessing the reliability of our predictions. ML models trained based on surface monitoring stations located in specific environments are indeed not expected to perform that well in locations with very different characteristics. To address this important issue, we introduced a simple although intuitive dissimilarity index (DI) that allows rejecting automatically areas where predictions can be considered as more doubtful (typically the mountainous areas). **Apart from the surface AQ in-situ observations, our methodology only relies on input dataset that are (1) free and open-source, (2) with global coverage, (3) well-recognized in the scientific community as high-quality and state-of-the-art, and (4) expected to be distributed over the long-term as they come from international organizations and scientific programs now well established. All these aspects are crucial in terms of near-future exploitation and commercialization as they offer the possibility to exploit such prototype on**

a large (global) market - thus at lower cost - and over the long-term, which makes it easier to amortize initial investments. To demonstrate its general applicability in different regions of the world, we applied our methodology to several regions of the world, including Central Chile, Denver and Front Range in Colorado, the Po valley in northern Italy, Catalonia in Spain, and Mexico City in Mexico. Interestingly, quite consistent results and performances were found in the different regions, despite very different environmental conditions. Importantly, this also allowed us to highlight its potential limitations when surface monitoring stations are too few and/or when they are located in too homogeneous environments, as was the case in Denver region (only 6 stations, all located in Denver city).

Although the expected performance of this first prototype was found to be reasonable, different directions can still be explored to further improve the predictive skills, for instance by testing a more extended set of ML models or by including additional input features. Regarding this last aspect, although its quality and level of detail is not equivalent in all regions of the world, the OpenStreetMap database could potentially provide useful additional information, in particular on the road network. Actually, in our work, we explored its use and were able to extract road information in some regions, but we faced some unexpected technical issues while trying to download data from the OpenStreetMap API in some of our domains. In order to keep the methodology and the set of input features identical in all regions, we finally decided to discard this source of information. For information purpose, we show in Fig. 32 the ML-based surface NO_2 concentrations over the Santiago de Chile region, with and without this additional road information. The OpenStreetMap-based road information here consists in 4 additional input features representing the gridded road density of 4 categories of roads, from minor streets to highways. Over this domain, this road information induced only very minor changes on the NO_2 fields and did not allow to improve the performance.

Figure 32: Annual average of ML-based surface NO_2 concentrations, without (left panel) and with (right panel) OpenStreetMap road density features, over the Santiago de Chile region.

It is also worth noting that although we focused here on the use of global-scale dataset, some other dataset of better quality might be available in some regions. The methodology described here is versatile enough to allow including higher-quality dataset available locally in specific

regions, to help further improving the predictive skills over the corresponding domain. For instance, the regional CAMS reanalysis over Europe has a much better spatial resolution than CAMSRA and could thus be used, in replacement or in complement of this last global-scale dataset. Importantly, in the hypothetical case where a CTM-based input feature would be very good for representing the NO₂ concentrations, the GBR models would attribute a dominant importance to this specific feature and discard the others. This would lead to NO₂ predictions very close to what was simulated with this CTM, likely without deterioration of its initial performance.

Due to the limited time available, we focused our study on the NO₂ pollutant and were not able to test our methodology on other pollutants, like particulate matter (PM) for which space-based Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) observations can provide some useful information. While the methodology developed for NO₂ would remain the same for PM, the expected performance of the ML models would probably be lower, considering the much higher complexity of PM compared to NO₂. Indeed, as a mainly primary chemical compound of relatively short lifetime, NO₂ remains close to its source and thus, it is probably one of the easiest pollutant to predict. Conversely, PM includes both primary and secondary chemical compounds, originating from numerous anthropogenic and natural sources, with much longer chemical lifetimes allowing a transport over long distances. Despite that, a number of studies already investigated the use of ML models to predict surface PM, often with satisfactory results. However, the aforementioned issue of the applicability of the trained ML models is typically ignored in most studies of the literature, which put some uncertainties regarding the reliability of the results.

4.7 Release of the product prototype for future exploitation

The product prototype developed in the frame of this work will be made freely available for exploitation under an open-source license under the name SAMARITAN v1.1 (*Space-bAsed Monitoring of AiR quality using mAchine learniNg*). We are currently discussing the license to be use with the BSC's technology Transfer team, but most probable candidates are the Apache License version 2.0 (<https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>) and the GNU General Public License version 3 (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>). The licensing process should be finalized early 2022. After that, the SAMARITAN code will be publicly released on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Note that the SAMARITAN code is released as is, without warranties and user support.

The development of the SAMARITAN product has been initiated at the beginning of the AQ-WATCH project and the product in its current version could be considered being at a Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 5 (*Technology validated in relevant environment*). Therefore, more efforts are needed to increase its readiness and allow a commercial exploitation. However, actors operating in the field of air quality and interested in developing such innovative EO downstream applications will benefit from the experience gained along this work. Based entirely on free and open-source codes and global-scale dataset, the product prototype described here offers the possibility for creating value over a large (theoretically global) market at a reasonable cost. Although it makes use of the outputs of highly sophisticated and state-of-the-art geophysical modeling systems, it does not require an in-depth scientific understanding of the underlying concepts behind these systems neither highly specialized skills for running them. In

its current version, it is based on a popular and widely used machine learning algorithm whose mastery is likely within the reach of most tech companies. While the main barrier would long have been the capacity to store large amounts of data used by the SAMARITAN software, this is no longer the case with the existing DIAS platforms where most of these geophysical input dataset are already available and ready to be used. The computational cost of running the SAMARITAN software also appears as reasonable on such platforms.

As a final conclusion, the work presented in the deliverable demonstrates that regarding the definition of the scientific and technical concepts as well as the easy access to large EO and non-EO dataset and computational resources, the development and deployment of such EO downstream applications is now at hand.

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is

X	The general public (PU)
X	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

Materials for the public and the audiences beyond the AQ-WATCH project have been disseminated through the AQ-WATCH website.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

Yes No

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

As mentioned in the final discussion, besides NO₂, we were initially planning to apply the designed methodology to the prediction of surface PM concentrations. However, developing this prototype and enabling it to run in a highly parallelized way on a supercomputer has required a considerable effort (especially for the preprocessing of TROPOMI and CLMS data), which has not let enough time to explore this other direction (8 person-months were attributed to this WP2/Task 2.5). Indeed, our product prototype has required to work directly with the TROPOMI L2 orbit files while the TROPOMI data finally used in the regional atlas were only available at a coarse resolution and monthly scale. Also, the proposal was planning to focus on the 3 target regions covered by AQ-WATCH. However, since no publicly available surface NO₂ in-situ observations could have been obtained during our period of study, we had to discard the Beijing region. Additionally, as we saw, too few monitoring stations were available in the Denver region. This motivates us to consider a few additional regions to demonstrate the general applicability of the proposed approach, while highlighting some potentials caveats. Finally, including health impact assessments based on the obtained results has been considered as too premature given that they require a detailed information on all the most relevant pollutants, as well as detailed socio-demographic data that were not available in the frame of this project.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The product prototype developed here could represent an interesting complement to the regional atlases developed in AQ-WATCH, especially in regions and/or time periods where the surface air quality is not well reproduced by the physics-based modeling systems used to feed the atlas.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- September 2020 : poster at the ESA EO Φ -week presenting the objectives and some preliminary results related to this work. The Φ -week is an annual event gathering a variety of people including academic and private-sector scientists and entrepreneurs from start-ups and larger companies, all interested in EO and artificial intelligence (more details can be found here : <https://phiweek.esa.int/>)
- Planned dissemination for 2022 : Most of year 2021 has been dedicated to the development of the product prototype. We plan to further disseminate this work in coming international conferences, such as the European Geosciences Union (EGU) conference (April 2022) or the ESA Living Planet Symposium (May 2022).

11 Full track of publications and IP

11.1 Peer reviewed articles

Given that the development of the product prototype ended in late 2021, no peer-reviewed articles have been yet submitted and published.

11.2 Publications in preparation or submitted

We plan to prepare a first scientific publication to describe the methodology and illustrate it in specific regions. At this stage, we foresee a submission to the *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* peer-reviewed journal.

11.3 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable:

In this section, we describe the intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable and the corresponding SAMARITAN product.

Type of IP rights: The Python code associated the product prototype described in this deliverable is planned to be released in open-source, in order to allow near-future exploitation. The licensing process is currently still on-going with the BSC's Technology Transfer Office, but the most probable license candidates are the Apache License version 2.0 (<https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0>) and the GNU General Public License version 3 (<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.en.html>). We expect to finalize the licensing process in the beginning of 2022.

Has the IPR protection been awarded?

Not yet, expected in early 2022.

If yes, please provide further details